

Addendum for the application of Lemenkova Polina, M.Sc for
PhD position at the Univerzita Karlova v Praze, Přírodovědecká fakulta
Duration: Three years (01st of September 2013 - 01st of September 2016)

Research Plan
“GIS mapping of the ecosystems in Šumava mountains, Czech republic”

for the PhD research of the Lemenkova Polina,
under the joint supervision of Prof. Dr. Pavel Kindlemann and Prof. Dr. Zdenka Krenova.

The study area is Šumava mountains region located on the southwestern border of the Czech Republic. The general PhD research idea lies in the multi-disciplinary project which requires investigation of mountain ecosystems using technical GIS skills and physical-geographic analysis of regional biodiversity, geomorphological-ecological and climatic settings of the area.

I. Geographical part. Physical-geographical part of the research will focus on evaluation of the current and past situation of the ecosystems in the study area: biodiversity, climate, landscapes, geomorphology (landforms), hydrological conditions (rivers Vltava, Otava and Úhlava). The main focus is to access and analyze current situation and (possible) changes in environmental settings of Šumava Mountains.

During this research part we suggest to analyze local geographic and ecological phenomena (as briefly described above) in Šumava region, and to assess landscape and environmental changes that may be not obvious in the satellite data. If possible, the field excursions to the area are suggested.

II. Technical part. During the GIS part it is suggested to intensely use geoinformatics and remote sensing (further RS) data for RS based research: GIS modelling, mapping and geodata processing. The GIS and RS data processing will support mapping part of the research: visualizing images, maps and plans of the region, performing geo-statistical analysis (depending on available data). My technical skills will be useful in GIS and RS part of the research, data collecting, processing, cartographic presentation and mapping.

During the PhD period we plan to publish provisional intermediate results (for example, covering part of the whole study area) in form of several (3-4) research papers in a journals. Additionally, presentations at conferences are proposed (both oral and as posters).

Research topic: Application of remote sensing data & GIS methods for spatial analysis of environmental landscape changes: case study of Šumava mountains

Research area: South-western area of Czech Republic, Šumava region

Introduction and actuality of research problem:

The study region of Šumava mountains and its surroundings is known for the unique and rich physical geography and environmental settings. The physical geography of the region combines diverse landforms, various geomorphological and natural landscapes, species and vegetation richness, untouched unique forest landscapes. The geomorphological settings of the area include wide variety of landforms. The region is being intensively visited by the tourists, due to its natural attractiveness, interesting natural and cultural sights, scenic landscapes and biodiversity richness. Besides recreation activities, the region is known for agricultural cultivation and farming activities. The purpose of this research is to analyze, how the environmental settings and landscapes in the Šumava mountains changed over the past decades, and to apply GIS for environmental mapping.

Research aims:

- 1) Ecoregions of Šumava mountains comparing to other mountain ranges in Czech Republic: comparison and brief overview
- 2) Environmental mapping of mountainous landscapes (Šumava district)
- 3) Spatial analysis of land cover types in Šumava mountains

Expected results:

- Analysis of the landscape changes in ecosystems of Šumava mountains
- Thematic maps of the land cover types in Bohemian forest, Šumava mountains
- Several articles (3-4) reporting the outcomes of the research work published in peer-reviewed journal (environment or earth sciences)
- Several presentations (4-5) in form of posters or slides at geoscience conferences
- Defended PhD Dissertation (by year 2016).

Research GIS data:

Data collecting.

1) Main geo-data materials at good quality and resolution will be taken from the available materials from the Přírodovědecká fakulta, Univerzita Karlova v Praze. These include following data: descriptive data, cartographic format files covering study area (e.g. ArcGIS shape files), local available materials from the faculty and university library: maps, books, topographic plans in large scales, reports and articles.

2) Additionally, coarse-resolution data from the GIS open sources will be taken for general mapping. These include aerial and satellite images covering different time span (10-20 years). Among available open sources we consider the following ones: satellite imagery from The Earth Explorer (<http://edcns17.cr.usgs.gov/NewEarthExplorer/>), The Earth Science Data Interface (<http://glcfapp.glc.f.umd.edu:8080/esdi/index.jsp>), GloVis (<http://glovis.usgs.gov/>), aerial images (Google Earth), free Digital Elevation Models from the open source <http://geomorphometry.org/>, ASTER GDEM www.gdem.aster.ersdac.or.jp/.

Technical background:

The research is technically based on available GIS software for geodata modeling (e.g. ArcGIS, MapInfo or any other available at lab). For satellite data processing it is proposed to use such software as Erdas Imagine, Idrisi GIS or ILWIS GIS.

Detailed research plan

§ 1. Starting working project

1. Data collecting.

The first, initial part of the research working plan includes:

- organizing all available collected geodata on the faculty's computer (on hard disk);
- discussing, overviewing and assessing these materials with supervisors and colleagues in order to become familiar with all available resources;
- starting GIS project, geo-referencing (where necessary), organizing geodata in ArcGIS / ILWIS

2. Data organizing.

Preparing GIS project with remote sensing data and basic vector ground layers for GIS mapping (§ 3):

1. Ground layer showing relief, based on DEM, geological and topographic maps

2. if necessary - urban main infrastructure of surrounding cities and towns Šumava mountains city and surrounding: street network, buildings, etc.
3. Land cover types and vegetation covering test sites in the surrounding mountains
4. Landscapes and important biogeographic areas within the mountains
5. Satellite images of the research area (Šumava) taken in different time (last 20-30 years)

§ 2. Spatial analysis in GIS project

- Spatial analysis of the thematic layers.

Spatial analysis of the geodata is aimed to perform physical-geographical overview and landscapes of the western Šumava mountains, Bohemian forest, as well as to analyze distribution of various land use types over the study region.

- Preparing thematic layers in *ArcGIS* and/or *ILWIS*: Geomorphological relief of Šumava, based on DEM and analysis of landscapes and land cover types
 - Performing image processing using supervised classification (ILWIS) for indication of land cover types in the Bohemian Forest
 - Environmental change detection: overlay of geodata (maps, satellite images and DEMs) using cartographic methods, to compare changes in landscape patterns at present and 10-20 years ago (time span 1990 – 2010).
 - Environmental corridors: regional studies of natural land cover types in Šumava mountains, Bohemian Forest province, typical for the test areas. Detection of changes in green patches and vegetation coverage. Application of the supervised classification (e.g., max. likelihood) to characterize main vegetation types in the surroundings mountains, and its dynamics over the past years (whether it is extending or regressing over time)
- Writing 2-3- article for the publications in a scientific journal, + presentation at thematic conferences.

§ 3. Thematic mapping: land cover types in Bohemian Forest

Thematic mapping is based on ILWIS / Arc GIS, using the results of the previous working step (§ 2, Spatial analysis...): visualizing changes in landscape structures and land cover during the last decades using overlay. Preparing cartographic layouts.

- Regional studies of Šumava surroundings: land cover types & landscape patterns
- Creating thematic maps detecting landscape dynamics since 1990
- Creating thematic maps demonstrating land cover types over the research area.

§ 4. Preparing final text of PhD dissertation

1. The cartographic results will be visualized as several thematic maps illustrating dynamics in land types in Šumava mountains, Bohemian Forest province, caused by global environmental changes.
2. Formatting text, graphics, diagrams, etc.: *“Environmental landscapes changes in Šumava mountains, Czech Republic”*.
3. Preparing final written version of dissertation.

26th of March, 2013.

Moscow / Prague

PhD applicant:

Polina Lemenkova, M.Sc.

Future scientific supervisors:

Prof. Dr. Pavel Kindlemann

Prof. Dr. Zdenka Krenova